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ABSTRACT

This report presents the summary of the scientific and technical discussions in the ARIES WP7 network on the development of rings with ultra-low emittance, the associated technological challenges for the design, construction and operation of such rings and the experimental activities supported with the ARIES WP7 programme.

The accelerator community working on ultra-low emittance ring has grown significantly in the last ten years, with the first machine beginning operation and many new project receiving funding. The development of such rings is underpinned by the use of strong gradient magnets with significantly reduced aperture with respect to the conventional accelerator design of the previous generation. Technological advances in magnets, vacuum, injection system and diagnostics have opened the route to ever more aggressive lattice designs, hence reducing the equilibrium emittance to tens of pm. This report review the main research topics in the accelerator science and technology of low emittance that were the focus of the WP7.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

The WP7 of the ARIES project aimed at supporting networking activities in the accelerator community involved in the construction and operation of ultra-low emittance rings. The progress in the field is underpinned by the solution of a new set of technological challenges in the design of key subsystem like injection, magnets and vacuum vessels, with significantly smaller apertures compared to the ones of third generation light sources in operation today. A wealth of novel concepts has been proposed and the corresponding technological challenges have been explored with strong R&D programmes. As a result, new more aggressive upgrade projects have opted for ambitious lattice design now reaching the few tens of pm. The Deliverable 7.4 consists in the report of the main activities and discussions of the whole network, held in the corresponding workshops, completed with a set of recommendations for the design upgrade and operation of ultra-low emittance rings.

1. Introduction

The R&D on ultra-low emittance ring has been driven by the High Energy Physics community and the light source community with the aim of designing and building damping rings, colliders and synchrotron light sources of ever increasing luminosity and brightness respectively.

The Multi-Bend Achromat (MBA) [1] concept has played a key role in this development. The first MBA storage ring was MAX IV (Lund, Sweden), in operation since 2016, followed by the ESRF-EBS (Grenoble, France) in 2020 and SIRIUS in 2021 (Campinas, Brazil). The present landscape is illustrated in Fig. 1 where the emittance of the ring normalised to the square of the energy is shown as a function of the circumference

Fig. 1: present landscape of operating light source (blue) and proposed MBA projects (red based on classical off axis injection, cyan based on novel on axis injection schemes)

The most advanced design target emittances below 100 pm by using strong focussing magnets, with gradients exceeding the 100 T/m in some projects. The consequences on the non-linear beam dynamics, injection system, vacuum chamber design, and diagnostics constitute a sequence of concatenated technical challenges that have to be solved for the successful operation of such machines.

These aspects have been the topics of ARIES WP7 (Rings for Ultra-Low Emittance - RUL ϵ) activities. WP7 has supported networking activities and several workshops, many of which dedicated to the specific aspects the design and technology of low emittance rings subsystems:

- First topical workshop on injection and injection systems for ultra-low emittance rings, TWISS, Bessy-II, Berlin (Germany), August 2017 [2]
- 7th General Low Emittance Ring network workshop, CERN, January 2018 [3]
- Topical workshop on diagnostics for ultra-low emittance rings, Chilton (UK), April 2018 [4]
- Topical workshop on commissioning of ultra-low emittance ring, KIT, Karlsruhe (Germany), February 2018 [5]
- Second topical workshop on injection and injection systems for ultra-low emittance rings, TWISS, PSI, Villigen (Switzerland), February 2019 [6]
- Advanced Low-Emittance Ring Technology (ALERT2019), with topical theme “rings with small apertures”, in Ioannina (Greece), July 2019 [7]
- 8th General Low Emittance Ring network workshop, (virtual meeting) INFN, Frascati, October 2020 [8]

These workshops have been well attended, usually by ~80 delegates for the general workshop and ~40 for the topical workshop, with a notable spike to 160 delegates for the virtual workshop in October 2020. The present report is a summary of the most recent developments in the field and of the main points discussed in the ARIES WP7 workshops. We present the summaries of the activities on injection system (Section 2) on the magnets (Section 3) on the vacuum system (Section 4) on the collective effect (Section 5) and on the beam tests (Section 6) supported in the ARIES programme.

2. Novel Injection Schemes for ultra-low emittance rings

The injection process in ultra-low emittance damping rings and light sources has posed increasingly tighter demands on the injector systems and the associated technologies. The main issues are related to the tight aperture available in such rings and to the requirement on fast kicker pulses to accommodate injection patterns with different bunch spacing. A list of the main ring parameter corresponding apertures and optics functions is reported in Table 1, for classical MBA and Hybrid MBA (HMBA).

	energy (Gev)	emittance (pm)	ener. spr. (1e-4)	β_x, β_y (m) @ source point	DA (mm), β (m) @ inj. point	LMA (%) TL (h)	reverse bends
ALS-U	2.0	108	9.8	2.0, 2.8	1.0 @ 2.0	2.5, (1.0)	yes
ELETTRA 2	2.4	212	9.3	5.7, 1.6	6.0 @ 5.7	4.0, (6.2)	yes
SLS-II	2.7	157	12.0	2.5, 1.3	7.0 @ 22.0	4.0, (6.3)	yes
SOLEIL-U	2.75	81	9.0	1.3, 1.3	5.0 @ 11.0	3.5, (3.3)	yes
Diamond II	3.5	136	9.0	6.0, 2.5	5.0 @ 6.0	1.6, (4.0)	yes
SIRIUS	3	250	8.5	1.5, 1.5	10.0 @ 17.0	3.7, (3.9)	no
APS-U	6	42	13.5	4.9, 1.9	2.2 @ 5.2	2.1, (4.0)	yes
ESRF-EBS	6	135	9.3	6.9, 2.6	8.0 @ 18.6	3.4, (20)	no
HEPS	6	<60 (35)	10	2.6, 2.3	1.0 @ 2.6	1.5, (1.0)	yes
PETRA IV	6	20	11.2	4.0, 2.0	3.6 @ 21.7	2.0, (1.2)	tbd

Black classical MBA - Blue HMBA or variations

Table 1: main parameters of ultra-low emittance storage rings

It is interesting to note that novel on-axis injection schemes allow another technological jump in the landscape of quasi-diffraction limited light sources as shown in Fig. 1.1, allowing injection in reduced apertures (and smaller emittance) or with less perturbation during the injection transient.

This leap in emittance is underpinned by the development of variety of new beam physics ideas, by technological advance in the design of kickers and striplines and, equally important, in the development of new pulsed power modulators. These three major aspects have been the topics of Task 7.2 in ARIES WP7 (Rings for Ultra-Low Emittance - RUL ϵ). The detailed results are summarised in the report associated to deliverable 7.2 [9], Here we review the main findings.

The difficulties in reducing the injection transient with classical four kickers orbit bump during injection has stimulated the design of new kickers with zero field on-axis so to leave the stored beam unperturbed during injection. This is the basic idea of the non-linear kicker (NLK) concept. that is a pulsed magnet providing a highly nonlinear magnetic field as shown in Fig. 2, such that the field at the centre is zero and it grows nonlinearly, in an octupole-like fashion, in the horizontal plane. In this way the stored beam, at the centre of the aperture does not experience any kick, while the injected beam, entering at the side (few mm) is kicked inside the dynamic aperture, provided the phase advance between septum and NLK are properly adjusted.

Fig. 2: Transverse dependence of the magnetic field in a NLK. Example taken from SOLEIL's NLK [10]

The original design proposed by BESSY-II [11] was built and installed in the ring in 2011. The BESSY II design was subsequently taken over by SOLEIL who built a NLK for the MAX IV ring. And is now routinely used in operation. Fig. 3 shows the reduction of the injection transient.

Fig. 3: Reduction of transient with MAX IV kicker [12]

Such NLK system are not easy to build and, in any case, they still require a significant transverse dynamic aperture of a few mm. For these reasons, a new series of injection schemes have been developed in the last years, based on more or less exotic variants of the concept of on-axis injection. Two strands can be immediately separated here. The on-axis injection allows accumulation or it is a swap-out injection where the existing beam is kicked out and fully replaced by a new incoming fresh beam. As before, the main issues to consider are a good injection efficiency and a transparent top-up.

On-axis injection with accumulation is achieved in the so-called longitudinal injection schemes, where the injected beam is timed to enter the ring in between the stored bunches and kicked on axis, by using the golf club acceptance (requires off-energy injection). In a machine operating with 500 MHz this would mean a zero-to-zero pulse duration of less than 4 ns (kicking only one bunch). In a 100 MHz machine, this time interval relaxes to 20 ns. Where possible this scheme could work well for those machines which operate with fill pattern that allow a bunch separation of 10 ns or

more. It is evident in any case that these schemes are enabled by the development of fast kicker and pulsers. An example of on-axis accumulation using off energy injection in the golf club longitudinal acceptance is shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5

Fig. 4: layout of the longitudinal off-energy injection scheme [13]

Fig. 5; golf club acceptance and injection [14]

On-axis injection with swap-out [16] is conceptually very simple in that it requires simply a fast kicker to drive the stored beam out and inject the new fresh beam on-axis. Such scheme however must consider the amount of charge that needs swapping out and the rate. Delivering the amount of charge present in the stored beam requires a high charge injector which can deal with pulses on the order of 10 nC or more. If a multi-bunch injection is used to relax the top-up repetition rate, we should consider that the injected bunches (with the injector emittance much larger than the main ring) will effectively create a loss of brightness for a few damping times. This aspect defeats the idea of transparent injection.

The development of the new injection schemes is supported by the corresponding development in high voltage fast pulsers based on solid-state high-power switches. An example of the most aggressive design is given in Fig. 6, shown the HEPS (Beijing, China) for a pulser based on an inductive adders switched by a drift step recovery diode (DSRD) to generate 17.4 kV in 4 ns pulses. Reliability tests for continuous operation 8 hours every day of 15 kV-15ns pulses at a repetition rate of 300 Hz were carried out for 4 weeks without problems.

Figure 6: fast kicker pulses at HEPS with inductive adders and DSRD [15]

Another interesting example is given by a commercial company [17] with pulsar delivering 4 ns Gaussian pulses zero-to-zero 10 kV that can be pushed to 3-5 kV in 2 ns zero-to-zero pulses (see Fig. 7), similar to the results reported by HEPS. Sydora pulsars are based on MOSFET switches.

Fig. 7: Sydora pulsar output with 2 ns Gaussian pulses of 3 kV peak voltage [17]

3. Magnets system for ultra-low emittance rings

Third generation light sources, operating with emittance in the order of few nm, required quadrupole gradients in the few tens of T/m, while the new generation, with emittance below ~100 pm, require gradients approaching the 100 T/m. Simple rule of thumb for the design of such magnet show that the bore radius of quadrupole is reduced from ~20-30 mm radius to ~10-15 mm radius. Furthermore, the quest for compact design has driven the development of new concepts like longitudinal gradient dipoles and the wider use of solutions based on permanent magnets.

Table 2 illustrates the range of gradients required in these new projects and the foreseen apertures.

	energy (Gev)	MAX b' T/m	MAX b'' T/m ²	MAX b''' T/m ³	min. bore radius (mm)
ALS-U	2.0	105	10500	n/a	12.0
ELETTRA 2	2.4	50	4000	45000	13.0
SLS-II	2.7	97	8000	270000	10.5
SOLEIL-U	2.75	<110	16000	1500000	8.0
Diamond II	3.5	85	7700	660000	12.0
SIRIUS	3	45	2400	n/a	14.0
APS-U	6	86	6300	n/a	13.0
ESRF-EBS	6	90	3200	37000	12.8
HEPS	6	80	7500	670000	12.5
PETRA IV	6	92	6400	330000	12.5

Table 2: ranges for magnet gradient in the main new generation of ultra-low emittance rings

For reaching high-gradient with electromagnetic quadrupoles, the current can be increased to the maximum permissible value, for a reduced bore radius. With the same technology (and same aperture), the gradient can be increased by using tapered poles and coils and raising the number of turns. An example for such a design is given in Fig. 8, where gradient for the upgrade of CLS is plotted versus Amp-turns (left) and good field region (right) for various apertures [20]. Different cobalt-iron magnetic alloys like vanadium permendur (Fe-Co) and type of poles can also be considered, as for the APS-U and ALS-U.

Fig. 8: Quadrupole gradient versus Amp-turns (left) and good field region (right) for various apertures (bore diameter), for the CLS 2 [20].

The resulting high-power consumption can be mitigated, within some limit, by the coil and pole design. At the same time, the field homogeneity is compromised by a current dependant dodecapole (b_6) multi-pole, which can be reduced with pole shaping. In that case, a trade-off with the maximum gradient is necessary. The second important challenge is reflected by the tight mechanical tolerances which comes naturally from the fact that small aperture magnets are more sensitive to mechanical errors. The magnetic error ΔB_n for multipole n at bore radius R is proportional to the mechanical error ε and inversely proportional to the bore radius. A mechanical tolerance of $\pm 40 \mu\text{m}$ is presently standard, whereas $\pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ is getting very expensive [17].

An overview of quadrupole gradient over the bore radius is plotted in logarithmic scale in Fig. 3.2 (left). The resistive magnets (red points) achieve gradients up to 105 T/m at a radius of 13 mm. They are easily tunable and present a good homogeneity, as they are iron-dominated. On the other hand, permanent material (PM) magnets offer gradient of up to 560 T/m at smaller radius of 2.5 mm and come with several designs and technology offering tunability or only fixed gradient values. As the dependence of the gradient to the bore radius is trivial, a better representation is given in the right plot of Fig. 9, where the equivalent field (product of gradient with radius) is plotted versus the bore radius. For resistive magnets, the usual range of the field is between 1.1 to 1.3 T. The equivalent for Halbach type PM quadrupoles can reach 1.5 T with large outer-to-inner radii ratio. The field can exceed 2 T for “super-strong” PM and hybrid quadrupoles, like the CLIC QD0. The target for high field would be probably higher than 1.5 T, with apertures between 5 and 10 mm, with a $\pm 5\%$ tuning range.

Fig. 9: Overview of quadrupole gradient G in T/m (left) and equivalent field $r_0 G$ (right) versus the bore radius r_0 [17].

Adjustable PM magnets including dipoles are also being considered and examples of such designs are shown in Fig. 10 for SPring-8 (left) and the CLIC drive beam turn-around loops (right).

Fig. 10: PM dipoles for SPring-8 (left) and the ZEPTO Dipole Design for the CLIC drive beam turn-around loops (right) [19].

Dipoles with longitudinal gradient are being considered in several low emittance rings for further lowering the horizontal emittance and for flexibility in the optics design, in particular dispersion manipulation [17, 18, 21, 22]. An example of such a design is pictured in Fig. 11, for the CLIC damping rings. This particular magnet achieves a maximum field of 2.3 T, while following a hyperbolic field profile decay, using different PM material and adjustable gap for the low, mid and high field region. At the same time a quadrupole gradient is introduced. This allows a reduction of the emittance by a factor of 7, as compared to the one of the standard Theoretical Minimum Emittance (TME) cell.

Fig. 11: Longitudinally variable dipole with gradient for the CLIC damping rings (left) and corresponding field profile variation along the magnet's length (right) [18].

4. Vacuum systems ultra-low emittance rings

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Small aperture vessels are characterised by a low vacuum conductivity, hence pumping with NEG coating has become the standard for supplementing the additional pumping in ultra-low emittance accelerators. Virtually all new projects employ NEG coating to some extent. The proposed solutions differ in the amount of chamber that is coated, ranging from coating both arcs and straight vessels to coating limited to simple vessel in the straight sections. NEG has also the additional benefit of reducing the photon desorption yield of the coated chamber. To clarify the characteristics of NEG coating, there are today quite a number of studies being made in different labs around the world including beam-based experiments. This is also one of the areas where industries are actively getting involved in research works including joint collaboration with laboratories, with an obvious reason of a huge market anticipated over the years to come on small aperture NEG coated vacuum chambers for future low-emittance rings.

4.2 ISSUES WITH NEG COATING

The main difficulties associated to coatings can be summarised in

- uniformity requirement on the coating
- impedance effect of the coating
- logistic in the activation procedure (in-situ vs ex-situ activation)

The coating thickness is a compromise between vacuum performance and the conductivity of the layer. Extensive studies performed at Daresbury Laboratories show that NEG thickness of up to 1 μm , provides good vacuum characteristics while not impacting the surface resistance of the material at the typical frequencies of interest (~ 10 GHz), which remains essentially that of the substrate [23]. Fig. 12 shows that changes in the impedance occur at frequency ranges that are generally too high for the typical bunch length for operation in ultra-low emittance rings. However,

achieving the required uniformity of the coating in complex geometries still remains a technology issue: 250 nm uniformity on a 2 μm thick coating was reported on the SLS NEG coating trials [24].

Fig. 12: Resistivity as a function of the NEG thickness for different frequencies. The yellow band indicates the typical values chosen in accelerators.

The impact of the coating on the resistive surface depends on the conductivity of the material and on the deposition process. The materials used (Titanium-Zirconium-Vanadium) generate a conductivity larger than Stainless Steel. Different material choices are still part of an intense R&D and it was recently reported that pure Zirconium has better sticking probabilities than Ti-Zr-V and comparable to more complex compounds such as Hf-Zr-V, Ti-Hf-V, Ti-Zr-Hf [23].

In situ activation is based prevalently on the use of heater tapes wound around the chamber to reach a temperature of 150-180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This choice requires space in the magnet bore aperture to allow the permanent installation of such heater tapes. Sirius experience shows that the thickness of these tapes can be reduced to 400 μm [26]. The activation temperature should be guaranteed to all the coated part and this is a potential problem in case of complex geometries (e.g. with keyslots or tapers). Experimental campaigns on the possibility of activating the NEG with synchrotron radiation are ongoing but no conclusive results are yet available.

There seems to be several technically feasible solutions regarding the extent to which NEG could be integrated in an innovative pumping system. There is today a trend to develop a vacuum system with fully coated chambers (MAX IV, SIRIUS, SOLEIL, PETRA IV), while other projects have opted for a mixture of NEG coating straight chamber with classical antechambers in the arcs (ESRF-EBS, Diamond II) while NEG coating for reduced photon desorption is the main reason for the full NEG coating proposed for SLS II [24].

As regards the metallic coating itself, special care should be taken of the Ti coating of ceramic chambers used in pulsed magnets in off axis injection schemes (e.g. septum and four kickers bump). In fact, any non-uniformity in the coating generates different effect on the magnetic field pulse, including transient oscillations in the stored beam during Top-Up. The process of coating is

eased by manufacturing procedures of the ceramic chamber involving the manufacturing of two separate halves, assembled by soldering along the midplane of the beam. This ensures precision machining of the inner part of the ceramic and a better quality of the coating [27].

For future ultra-low emittance rings, a big technical challenge in using NEG coating lies in the feasibility of uniform coating in small aperture beam pipes as well as in assuring the pumping efficiency as in larger dimension chambers. The latter is not obvious as the efficiency of pumping depends on the balance with the dynamic PSD process. To give answers to the critical question, a beamline has been constructed at SOLEIL (see Fig. 13) so to be able to measure the pumping efficiency of various beam pipes differing in pipe diameter exposed to synchrotron radiation in comparison with predictions given by simulation [42]. For the upgraded ring of SOLEIL, use of NEG coated chambers having merely 10-12 mm internal diameter is planned to cope with an ultra-low emittance lattice giving the emittance of 80 pm-rad [43].

Fig. 13: A Photon Stimulated Desorption (PSD) test beamline developed at SOLEIL [42]

4.3 CONTRIBUTIONS OF INDUSTRIES

As mentioned in 4.1 there is notable involvement of industries in the development of novel vacuum systems for modern and future low-emittance rings today due first to the scale of the market existing around the world and secondly to the R&D aspects which are still required in building them. Reflecting this fact, it is impressive to note that out of five contributions in the vacuum technology session of LER2020 workshop, three were from the industries [44, 45,46]. In the presentation of [45], in particular, it was stated that the company is capable of depositing large batches of chambers with diameters down to 6 mm to be NEG coated. In the PSD beamline developed at SOLEIL referred to above in 3.2, this company is making a joint study with SOLEIL being in charge of providing NEG coated chambers of various dimensions. In another contribution from the industries, technical difficulties and efforts associated with the general trend of miniaturization of vacuum components were presented, well addressing the growing issues related

to geometric and resistive-wall wake fields that provoke beam instability and beam-induced heating, concluding that the future of the vacuum component vendors is expected to remain busy [44].

4.4 VACUUM RELATED CHALLENGES FOR FCC-EE

A series of challenges in the vacuum technology exist in designing FCC-ee, an extremely large-scaled high energy lepton collider project pursued at CERN, which consists of two 100 km long rings (booster + storage ring) for e+e- collision producing Z, W, Higgs bosons top particles. These challenges are quite distinct in nature from those of low-emittance rings for synchrotron radiation sources [47]. The major requirements that came up through the R&D studies carried out so far are:

- Industrial scale mass production of easy to fabricate vacuum components for the two 100 km long rings.
- Very low-loss and low impedance vacuum components to with stand low-emittance, high luminosity and high intensity beams.
- Use of chamber materials which make the rings free from electron clouds and ions. - Minimize the vacuum conditioning time.

All previously developed vacuum technologies for colliders such as LEP and SuperKEKB are to be considered, re-used and extended. Future works towards TDR shall focus on:

- Design and integration of vacuum chambers and components (e.g. low-loss, low/impedance RF contact fingers) within the common-yoke arc dipoles and quadrupoles.
- Beam-based tests of chambers and vacuum components at existing rings such as KARA and DAFNE.
- Identification of electron cloud mitigation surface treatments for the e+ ring (e.g. laser ablation, NEG-coating, amorphous carbon), with particular attention to industrialization of the process and related cost issues.

5. Collective effects in ultra-low emittance rings

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Impedance and collective effects were much discussed in the topical workshop ALERT 2019 [12], as well as in the general workshop LER2020 [8], reflecting the high degree of concern of the community on the related subjects. There were conventionally studies reporting the optimization of vacuum components to minimize the impedance for future low-emittance rings whether they are synchrotron radiation sources or high energy colliders. A point of common interest for the two communities was the impact of impedance arising from a thin coating (typically of a micron to sub-micron level thickness) on the inner surface of the vacuum chamber wall, which can be generally classified in two categories: One is the metallic coating of poor conducting materials (such as NEG) made on a good conductor wall (such as copper). The other is the coating of good conducting materials (such as titanium) on dielectric walls to mitigate the impedance issues. There

is a clear trend today that modern synchrotron rings make intensive use of both types of thin coatings for good technical grounds. The overall characteristics of the impedance of coated chambers, in particular their frequency dependence, must, as a consequence, be well understood theoretically, numerically and experimentally. Whereas, one clear trend emerging in the light source community is the use of harmonic cavities (HCs) to lengthen an electron bunch thereby to increase the otherwise severely Touschek limited lifetime of an ultra-low emittance beam. Adverse collective effects possibly driven by an extended RF system (main + HC) are being addressed. Ongoing studies by the CERN group on the negative impact of detuning wakes on transverse single bunch instability, recently discovered, were presented and discussed.

5.2 ONGOING STUDIES FOR FUTURE ULTRA-LOW-EMITTANCE RINGS

A review on impedance and beam instabilities created by low gap vacuum chambers was given [28]. Though it is a global trend of accelerators today to go for lower gaps, it is particularly true for all ultra-low emittance rings under design and built in the light source community, known as DLSRs (Diffraction Limited Storage Rings). These rings utilise the MBA (Multi-Bend Achromat) principle of dividing dipoles into many pieces and strongly focus the beam at each of them towards the TME (Theoretical Minimal Emittance) condition. The strong focusing in turn requires low gap chambers in the magnet sections to have smaller distance between magnetic poles. A table and a figure were shown summarizing the global trend for half gap b 's (or inner radius of a cylindrical pipe in the arcs) considered for some of the typical rings under design or construction (Fig. 14 (left)), where the values tend to be below 10 mm. As a marked case, SOLEIL is currently considering employing b of down to 5 mm for the magnet sections for its upgrade. Another noticeable trend is that several different b values are considered within the magnet sections such as for ESRF-EBS, reflecting the effort to maximise the aperture where it is possible for better beam dynamics and lifetime performance.

Fig. 14: (left) Principal vertical half aperture b adopted in several existing and future light sources versus their machine energies; (right) Transverse impedance budget obtained for SIRIUS (taken from F.-E. De Sá, LER2016)

Such small b values for the beam duct create vacuum pumping issues. Here, one of the most promising solutions considered is NEG coating on the inner surfaces, as it has already been seen to work successfully in several rings such as MAXIV as the last good example [29]. In view of

relatively poor electric conductivity of the constituents of NEG (titanium, zirconium and vanadium), the impact of NEG coating on the machine impedance must be well understood. Studies indicate that thin NEG coating (micron level) on the inner surface of ordinary metallic chambers, in the normal frequency range seen by the beam, does not modify much the real part of the impedance, which is normally responsible for beam instabilities, while the imaginary part is increased by roughly a factor of two, suggesting that physical phenomena such as bunch lengthening and coherent detuning would be enhanced [30].

Considering the b -dependence of the machine impedances, whether they are of geometric or resistive-wall origins, which scale typically as b^{-1} longitudinally and b^{-3} transversely, it must be said that more effort is required to optimise the geometrical and material aspects of vacuum components to keep the same level of machine impedance as earlier rings of the same size. However, it must be pointed out that for MBA lattices there is a general trend that the average beta functions are lower than those of the earlier rings. One may therefore anticipate that in the transverse plane the increased impedance is effectively compensated. Novel BPM and the so-called impedance-free flanges developed for SIRIUS can be listed as good examples of the effort in this direction [31]. The impedance budget built for SIRIUS (Fig. 14 (right)) shows the typical situation where the resistive-wall impedance is dominating the budget and that due to NEG coating, the imaginary part is found nearly double as compared to the real part in the main frequency range of interest as pointed out earlier.

Preliminary studies of the resistive-wall instability were made for the SOLEIL upgrade using a Vlasov solver in the frequency domain, where lowering of the instability threshold for smaller b 's ($\phi = 2 \times b$ in the figure) is clearly found (Fig. 15 (left)).

Fig. 15: (left) Vertical resistive-wall instability threshold computed using a frequency domain (Vlasov type) method for SOLEIL upgrade; (right) Beam loss observed at SOLEIL originating in beam induced vacuum chamber heating [30].

The impact of the linear optics, optics nonlinearity, as well as harmonic cavity lengthening that are expected to influence (mitigate) significantly the coherent motions must be studied systematically. Simulation tools need to be extended accordingly to be able to incorporate these

effects. Regarding the impedance, not only must we care for beam instability, but generally the beam-induced heating of vacuum components gives more stringent tolerance, as an incidence on a single component may block the machine operation. The persistent beam loss existing at SOLEIL when it is operated at 500 mA in $\frac{3}{4}$ fill is understood to be caused by beam-induced machine heating that in turn produces local outgassing leading to FBII (Fast Beam-Ion Instability) [32]. Since transverse bunch-by-bunch feedback is constantly running to fight against resistive-wall instability, the sudden appearance of FBII which keeps getting stronger leads finally to a beam loss (Fig. 15 (right)).

A study of longitudinal single bunch instability was presented by A. Citterio (PSI) [33]. The main concern is understanding if the momentum compaction α , which is tuned to negative or to a very small value in magnitude due to the ultra-low emittance lattice design, enhances the instability to an unacceptable level. Here again we encounter a situation where a continued effort to improve the lattice performance ends up creating a significant impact on the collective effects. Related to this study, a dedicated experiment with beam was carried out in April 2019 at KARA among KARA, SOLEIL and PSI under the support of ARIES (WP7-WP11), to measure the microwave instability threshold as a function of the value of α , where the measured data suggested that the threshold is lowered when α is negative [34]. Numerical studies carried out by SLS for SLS-II focused upon the dependence of instability on α , the NEG and bunch lengthening with harmonic cavities (active and passive) (Fig. 16 (right)). Of particular interest and importance for the community is that the group managed to use two tracking codes, *elegant* and *mbtrack* and crosschecked the results, such as on the threshold and intensity-dependent bunch profiles, where the overall agreement was found to be quite satisfactory (Fig. 16). Such efforts are highly appreciated by the entire community. From these studies it was confirmed that NEG does not worsen the threshold and that the threshold is lower when α is negative. The last outcome, along with the experimental results at KARA gave the SLS team some elements to reconsider their negative α lattice for SLS-II.

Fig. 16: (left) Beam energy spread versus single bunch current calculation using the codes *Elegant* and *Mbtrack* including passive or active harmonic cavities, to identify the microwave instability threshold indicated with an arrow; (right) Comparison between *Elegant* and *Mbtrack* of the longitudinal bunch profile as a function of bunch current

5.3 SEMI-ANALYTICAL CHARACTERISATIONS OF SURFACE IMPEDANCE

Semi-analytical methods for obtaining the coupling impedance of beam ducts that have some specific conditions on their inner surface, typically layers of coating, are investigated. C. Zannini of CERN in [12] presented an overview of the subject showing how the impedance can be classified, with terms such as those due to geometric variations and to material-dependent or electric conductivity related origins. Evaluation methods of the impedance (analytical, numerical 3D, bench measurement) were also reviewed. Then, more detailed properties of the non-geometric impedance were presented. The relative importance of the impedance of coated chambers in modern accelerators was highlighted. It was shown how the longitudinal and transverse impedance can be decomposed into products of a geometric form factor depending on the chamber cross sections (known as the Yokoya factor), another geometric factor related to the chamber radius b , and to the part depending on the materials of the chamber determining the frequency-dependent EM characteristics of the impedance (Fig. 17 (left)). Examples were shown such as how the impedance of a ceramic chamber can be reduced with a thin titanium coating (Fig. 17 (right)).

Fig. 17: (left) Illustration of how the longitudinal and transverse impedances are composed of geometric form factors, chamber radius and material properties-dependent surface impedance; (right) Illustration of how metallic coating reduces the ceramic chamber impedance

The second contribution was given by S. Arsenyev, who presented the details of the surface impedance which was introduced in the former. Again the main focus of the latter was on the non-geometric impedance. In contrast to the field matching technique which is widely known and applied to obtain the impedance of coated materials such as those available today with the code IW2D developed at CERN, it was shown that there is another effective method by solving for the surface impedance. How coupling impedance is related to the surface impedance under the Leontovich boundary condition under the assumption $|\epsilon_1 \mu_1| > \epsilon_0 \mu_0$, and how the surface impedance can be obtained were presented (Fig. 18 (left)). Some specific examples of this approach were shown solving the surface impedance in problems such as the two-layer model, linear conductivity model and surface roughness model (Fig. 18 (right)) [35].

Fig. 18: (left) Illustration of how longitudinal and transverse impedance of a beam pipe can be related to the surface impedance; (right) measured surface roughness and its modelling to obtain the surface roughness impedance via surface impedance

5.4 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION OF COATING MATERIALS

Development of a bench measurement to perform electromagnetic characterisation of coating materials in the sub THz range and its application to NEG coating was presented by A. Passarelli (INFN, University of Naples, CERN). The objective was to develop a reliable, handy and inexpensive system for the electromagnetic characterisation of coating materials in the sub THz range. A time domain THz spectrometer TERA K15 was employed. A special circular wave guide was designed and fabricated at CERN (Fig. 19 (left)). The EM characterisation is made by measuring the signal attenuation inside a DUT with coating deposited. The process was first evaluated analytically and compared with numerical simulations using CST, where good agreement was obtained. Two NEG coated slabs (3.96 and 3.68 μm coating thickness) were then measured. The results were consistent between the two slabs and the fitted electric conductivity of roughly $8 \times 10^5 \text{ S/m}$ was also in agreement with expectations (Fig. 19 (right)) [36].

Fig. 19: (left): Illustration of DUT (Device under Test) arrangement; (right): Experimentally obtained electric conductivity of a NEG coated slab fitted from the bench measurement data

5.5 HARMONIC CAVITIES RELATED STUDIES

Reflecting the importance of harmonic cavities (HCs) in practically all upcoming and future low-emittance rings in the light source community, advanced studies of how they can impact the collective beam dynamics in combination with the main RF cavities were reported and discussed from several labs [48, 49, 50]. Regarding the choice of HCs, i.e. whether active or passive, and whether normal or superconducting, the major characteristics were reviewed [48], pointing out advantages and disadvantages, whose impact shall much depend upon the operational goals of a storage ring. In terms of bunch lengthening itself, it must be noted that the flat potential condition can practically not be attained in a passive scheme and that the bunch profile tends to be significantly non-Gaussian and asymmetric. For the SOLEIL upgrade case, a superconducting passive solution is nonetheless optimal as it enables lengthening a low total intensity high single bunch current mode (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20: Calculated performance of a superconducting 3rd HC for bunch lengthening in different beam fills as a function of the bunch position with the SOLEIL-U parameters [48]

Figs. 21: Simulated impact of $l = 0$ and $l = 1$ AC Robinson instability observed in the ALS-U case on the beam energy spread [50]

Several interesting new beam dynamics techniques developed were discussed: A matrix method that allows following accurately the transient beam loading induced by an arbitrary beam filling [49], as well as an extended Haissinski solver using the Newton's method that allows obtaining accurately without numerical failures the distorted bunch profiles of all bunches systematically in a bunch train [50]. In the study made for MAX-IV, the synchrotron tune spread was compared between those of intrabunch (due to the potential nonlinearity) and intrabunch (due to transient beam loading), where the latter was found to dominate the former, being the importance source of beam stabilisation against the main cavity (MC) HOM-induced coupled bunch instability [49]. The importance of investigating the AC-Robinson instability induced by the combined MC-HC system was commonly pointed out in evaluating the performance of a given bunch lengthening system. A detailed analysis was reported from ALS-U team employing both a semi-analytical approach deducing a stability diagram and numerical multibunch tracking, where $l=1$ coupled-bunch mode AC Robinson instability was found responsible for the stability limit, interestingly excited by the imaginary part of the cavity impedance. Numerical simulations revealed failure of longitudinal feedback in stabilising the beam against this instability when subtle differences existing among bunches are taken into account, where the beam energy spread may also be blown up due a combined $l = 0$ and $l = 1$ coupled-bunch instability possibly involving also higher bunch azimuthal modes (Fig. 21).

5.6 CERN STUDIES

A series of interesting studies ongoing at CERN were discussed, which were triggered from a recent unexpected finding in a study for the CERN PS ring [51] that, detuning wakes that arise from the vacuum chamber cross section asymmetry could render a beam unstable, while it was considered on the contrary that it prevents coupling of the modes induced by driving (dipole) wakes, thereby providing more stability. Several different approaches were taken to elucidate the

finding: A study using the circulant matrix formalism with an airbag model for a bunched beam and a constant wake, no detrimental effect of the detuning wake was found in the TMCI regime as long as the bunch is short, while it was found that for a long bunch, the contrary is true regarding the coupling of higher-order azimuthal modes [53]. In the two-particle mode, on the other hand, no such effect was found and the detuning wake could only bring about beneficial effects [54]. Instead, in a study where a coasting beam formalism was employed and the detuning wake contribution was added in parallel to the driving wake, a coupling appeared between the fast and slow waves in the horizontal plane, namely in accordance with the finding in the CERN PS study, in following the most unstable modes (Figs. 22) [52]. The newly developed coasting beam theory is therefore intended be extended, by taking into account the longitudinal degree of motions, chromaticity as well as energy spread.

Figs. 22: Demonstration of a coasting beam becoming horizontally unstable due to coupling between the most unstable mode fast and slow waves induced by the detuning wake (left), while the beam remains stable vertically (right) [52]

5.7 SUMMARY

With decreasing gaps of many of the future ring vacuum chambers, the beam coupling impedance is expected to get furthermore enhanced. Along with lattice designs pushing towards technical limits on their side, the evaluation of collective effects is confronted to take also into consideration nonlinear single particle dynamics to draw correct conclusions. Impedance arising from thin metallic coating of poor electric conducting materials on a good conductor wall or coating of good conducting materials on dielectric walls must be well understood and controlled both theoretically, numerically and experimentally. Works presented in the session go well along this direction showing the state-of-the-art progress. Simulation studies using different codes have shown good ways to benchmark codes and better confirm obtained results. Effect of NEG coating on beam instabilities requires further thorough studies.

6. Beam tests and commission strategies for ultra-low emittance rings

The ARIES-WP7 has supported the experimental tests on a number of critical points for the design and operation of low emittance rings. These include joint experimental sessions taken place for a beam test and a workshop aiming to the beam tests and commissioning of LERs.

6.1 BEAM TESTS FOR BEAM INJECTION AND EXTRACTION ISSUES

Typically, the LERs assume a multiple-bend achromatic lattice to reduce the beam emittance significantly. The trade-off is, however, such rings tend to have a narrow dynamic aperture. From the view of beam injection, a conventional injection scheme by an injection bump orbit seems unavailable any more for such rings. Still, the other method, so-called on-axis injection, seems one of the promising ways. As reported already in the first deliverable (D7.1) [55], a beam test for such a novel injection scheme has been carried out at BESSY-II. In the experiment, they injected the beam successfully by the on-axis method with an off-energy injection beam. Such an injection scheme, so-called "longitudinal injection", does not always have an injection rate comparable to that of the conventional method. Nonetheless, this result has become a benchmark to consider the possibility of the application to the LERs. At BESSY-II, aiming at the injection issue for the LERs, a beam test with a systematic measurement for the beam transport line has been carried out [56]. A reasonable beam injection rate needs to optimize the storage ring and the beam transport line optics. In this beam test, they have performed parameter-scans for the beam transport line at BESSY-II to simulate a commissioning procedure for the LERs. In the report [56], they have also discussed a strategy for the commissioning of beam transport lines in the LERs. On the other hand, a beam test for an extraction stripline kicker of the CLIC Damping Ring has been performed at ALBA [57]. They installed the stripline kicker in ALBA with additional BPMs around it and performed the beam test to measure the kick angle by the stripline kicker with the required precision. They have also completed the impedance characterization of the stripline kicker by using real beams.

6.2 BEAM TESTS FOR INSERTION DEVICES

It is highly expected to achieve a high brilliance synchrotron radiation beam by using high-performance insertion devices in the LERs. A beam commissioning for such insertion devices in the LERs could be an issue. KIT and the company Bilfinger Noell GmbH have developed a superconducting undulator [58, 59]. They have installed it into the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator (KARA) to perform beam tests to do the undulator's commissioning. After the off-line measurement, they installed the superconducting undulator (SCU20) into KARA and performed the beam commissioning successfully without deterioration of the stored electron beam. They measured the undulator radiation spectrum at the beamline for the insertion device with good agreement between the designed and measured values. The undulator SCU20 is in operation and delivers a high-quality synchrotron radiation beam to the beamline users [58, 59]. This result

suggests a possibility for the application of the superconducting undulators to the LERs in the future strongly.

6.3 BEAM TESTS FOR ORBIT FEEDBACKS

For the low emittance light sources, beam control of the linear optics is essential. The LOCO method is one of the vital tools to investigate the linear optics of the ring. One issue for LOCO is the time that is needed to complete the measurement for a whole storage ring. The orbit response matrix tends to be larger because of the number of the BPMs in the ring, leading to a significantly longer time for the measurement. At Diamond Light Source, they have developed a fast LOCO system [60] that can reduce the measurement time drastically and performed beam tests by optimizing excitation parameters for the fast LOCO. The fast LOCO measurement results agreed with the conventional LOCO, which suggests a possibility of the application to a fast optics correction system in the LERs.

6.4 BEAM TESTS FOR LOW- AND NEGATIVE MOMENTUM COMPACTION FACTORS

There are several schemes and strategies to realise ultra-low emittance rings. One of the promising methods is to optimise the dispersion function over the whole ring circumference to reduce the natural emittance. One of the results that accompany such lattice designs is visible on the momentum compaction factor. Due to the optimisation of the dispersion function, the momentum compaction factor tends to be significantly low. Consequently, such a condition leads to a short bunch length with higher electron density. Also, it leads to the generation of coherent synchrotron radiation (CSR), which brings a deterioration of the electron beam quality due to the microbunching instability.

In collaboration with ARIES-WP11 the capacity of Transnational Access at KARA in KIT was used to perform beam tests in low momentum compaction to investigate the longitudinal beam dynamics of the microbunching instability accompanied by the CSR generation [61]. At KARA, they use dedicated diagnostic with turn-by-turn and bunch-by-bunch resolution and with long-term observation periods. For the emitted CSR in the THz range, they achieve such a resolution with a diode detector and an ultrafast readout electronics KAPTURE [62, 63, 64]. For the longitudinal bunch profile, they use an electro-optical (EO) near-field setup, which has been installed into the storage ring. Due to the combination between the EO setup and grating with the line array detector KALYPSO [65,66], these beam diagnostic systems enables them to observe the CSR generation and the longitudinal phase space simultaneously with excellent time resolution for long periods.

The other option for the momentum compaction factor in the LERs is to set the factor to a negative value. In such a condition, the chromaticities must be negative during negative alpha operation to avoid head-tail instability. This allows to relax the sextupole magnetic field strength, and therefore the dynamic aperture to be significantly expanded, which then leads to an increased lifetime. At KARA in KIT, they have performed beam tests in negative momentum compaction factor (negative alpha) condition to investigate beam dynamics accompanied by such operating condition. The first deliverable report D7.1 for this Work Package WP7 reported the successful

beam commissioning for negative alpha operation at KARA [55]. After the first deliverable, the commissioning was continued. The stored beam current could be successfully increased from 30 μA (as reported in the deliverable report D7.1) to beyond 25 mA [67] at the injection energy of 500 MeV. By adjusting the bunch-by-bunch feedback system and transverse working points, they have established a range of negative alpha operation points whose value is between -1.2×10^{-2} and -1.2×10^{-3} . In such a negative alpha condition, they have confirmed the chromaticities in both directions had negative values. They also found that the vertical sextupole magnets significantly affected the beam injection rate under the negative alpha condition [34]. Such tendency strongly suggests suppression of the head-tail instability with negative chromaticity under the negative alpha operation. For further investigations of negative alpha beams, they have carried out an energy ramp while keeping the momentum compaction factor negative. So far, under the negative alpha condition, they have succeeded to ramp the energy up to 0.9 GeV [13]. Under the negative alpha in different beam energy conditions, they have also measured CSR in the THz region [67] to investigate the microbunching instability. Figure 23 shows the result of CSR measurement under the negative alpha operation at different beam energies. For both energies the measured data shows outbursts of the CSR intensity. As seen in the figure, the CSR bursts happen quasi-periodically, indicating the presence of the microbunching instability. For the two different machine settings the period and the temporal length of the bursts differ significantly.

Fig. 23: Measurements of the emitted coherent synchrotron radiation (CSR) at negative momentum compaction operation at 500 MeV and at 900 MeV beam energy. The typical bursting structure is visible in both cases. Both measurements were taken at roughly 0.18 mA bunch current [S5].

6.5 JOINT MEASUREMENTS AT KARA, SOLEIL AND SLS

At the beginning of the negative alpha operation's commissioning stage at KARA in KIT, KIT members have performed a joint measurement session with participants from SOLEIL and PSI. The joint session took place on 16th and 17th April 2019 at KARA. The negative alpha conditions were improved to get a better beam current and beam lifetime during this session. In parallel, they had a trial to observe a bunch-shortening phenomenon [68] that is one of the typical phenomena under negative alpha operation. It is predicted theoretically that the bunch shortening can occur from potential-well distortion due to an inductive impedance below the threshold beam current of the microwave instability. They improved the beam injection rate and beam conditions at the negative alpha operation during the joint session. These hints they got in the joint session led them

to a concrete commissioning strategy for negative alpha operation. Thanks to the strategy, so far, they can get a good beam current and quality, as mentioned above. Observation of the bunch-shortening phenomenon remains open and is to be investigated both from experimental and theoretical sides.

6.6 WORKSHOP ON BEAM TESTS AND COMMISSIONING OF ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE RINGS

Additionally to the efforts in beam tests for the LERs, an ARIES workshop was organised [69] as part of ARIES Work Package 7, RULE, and co-supported by ARIES Work Package 6, APEC. With more than 80 participants from 29 scientific laboratories in 16 countries, the workshop took place at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology from 18 to 20 February 2019 under the title “Beam Tests and Commissioning of Low Emittance Storage Rings”. 37 presentations were given in 8 sessions distributed over 3 days:

1. Motivations, lessons and projects overview
2. Injectors and injection
3. Insertion devices
4. Diagnostics, controls, automation, and feedbacks
5. High current effects
6. Low emittance
7. Optics design, measurements and corrections
8. Summary.

The workshop focused on beam tests and commissioning of low emittance rings such as MAX-IV and SuperKEKB. In the first part of the workshop, lessons and several strategies for 4th generation synchrotron light sources such as MAX-IV, SLS-II, ESRF-EBS, APS-U, PETRA-IV, and HEPS were presented. In the second part, some injectors' requirements and new injection schemes such as on-axis injection for the low-emittance rings were discussed and introduced. The third part consisted of presentations about insertion device performance and commissioning for in-vacuum and superconducting undulators. In the fourth part, several topics for automated commissioning plans, electric and optical beam diagnostic instrumentation and systems as well as beam feedback systems aimed at the commissioning of ultra-low emittance rings were presented. The fifth part was reserved for topics of high current effects, which contained a comparison of impedance beam-based measurements and simulations. Additionally, experimental verification of impedance modelling was a topic there. In the sixth part, three presentations took place: low emittance and luminosity tuning from SuperKEKB and emittance tuning from FCC-ee. Besides, the dynamic aperture problem in low-emittance rings was also discussed there. Optics measurements, tuning, and design topics with respect to commissioning for storage rings and negative alpha operation mode were presented and discussed in the seventh part. A focus was set on preparation procedures, components, and tests necessary for commissioning the upcoming low emittance rings, like ESRF-EBS, SIRIUS, HEPS, ALS-U, PETRA-IV etc. Similarities and synergies with future circular colliders were outlined [69].

7. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

ARIES WP7 has dealt with the major technological issues in the development of ultra-low emittance rings, consisting in the design of new injection schemes, innovative magnets design, vessel and vacuum concept with reduced aperture where the concept of NEG coating is extensively used. Many other technical subsystems have to adapt to such reduced apertures. A large number of novel technical solutions have emerged and have been reviewed in general and topical workshops supported by ARIES project, to be applied in the future ultra-low emittance projects.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
CSR	Coherent Synchrotron Radiation
DLSR	Diffraction Limited Storage Ring
DSRD	Drift Step Recovery Diode
EO	Electro-Optical
MBA	Multi-Bend Achromat
HC	Harmonic Cavities
HMBA	Hybrid MBA
LER	Low-Emittance Ring
MC	Main Cavity
NEG	Non-Evaporable Getter
NLK	Non-Linear Kicker
PM	Permanent (magnetic) Material
PS	Proton Synchrotron
PSD	Photon Stimulated Desorption
TME	Theoretical Minimal Emittance

MAX IV, ESRF-EBD, SIRIUS, BESSY-II, SOLEIL, APS-U, ALS-U, CLIC, PETRA IV, FCC – ee, KARA, SLS-II are different accelerators built or in design phase, employing ultra-low emittance rings.